

Research Article

Adoption of Agricultural Innovations: A Case Study of Technologies Developed by
National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM)

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Abstract

This study was carried out in Ifelodun Local Government Area (LGA) of Kwara State, Nigeria. The major source of livelihood and occupation of the people in the area is farming. Cassava and Okro are predominantly grown in the area; this informed the choice of the Centre to develop processing machines for these crops (i.e Cassava peeling tool and Okra slizer). A 2-stage sampling technique was employed for the study. The first stage involved the purposive selection of four communities namely; Ganmo, Fufu, Idofian and Jimba-Oja. In the second stage, a random sampling technique was used to select 50 farmers. An interview schedule with a structured questionnaire were administered to the farmers. Data collected were subjected to various degree of descriptive statistical analysis which include; ratios, frequencies and percentages. The result from this study showed that the adoption of these two NCAM technologies will enhance the livelihood of farmers, it also show that there is low level of awareness on the agricultural technology in the study area which is attributed to lack of extension materials. The study further reveals that majority (62%) of the respondents have strong desire to adopt the cassava peeling tool while 80% and 74% of the respondents agreed that the cassava peeling tool and okro slizer were respectively affordable compared to the local technology. 82% and 88.9% of the respondents showed keen interest and willingness to adopt cassava peeling tool and okro slizer respectively. The findings from this research work showed clearly the level of adoption of these two technologies as evident from the respondents' submission. In order to enrich this stand, the study recommended that; there is need for adequate publicity of NCAM technologies to create awareness among farmers and the general public, extension officers should be fully involved right from the planning stage, and extension component of NCAM should be strengthened to enable it meet the challenges of technology assimilation and adoption.

Keywords: Adoption, Cassava, Okro, NCAM, Extension, Technology

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Introduction

The role of agriculture in Nigeria's economic development and food security needs no emphasis. This is because it provides employment to over 75 percent and meets close to 90 percent of the food requirements of the population; apart from providing raw materials for Nigeria's industries, agriculture contributes about 40 percent to the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and accounts for 45 percent of total non-oil export (NBS, 2009; Falusi 2010). However, agricultural productivity has consistently declined compared to population growth over the years. This can be attributed to low adoption of agricultural research results and technologies that can increase farmer's productivity. Technology adoption means different things to different people. To some, it is viewed as a consistent process, the key to enabling hesitant users to successfully adopt and use technology. Technology adoption is important because it is the vehicle that allows most people to participate in a rapidly changing world where technology has become central to our lives. Individuals who would not or cannot adopt will be increasingly limiting their ability to participate fully in the convenience and financial benefits associated with technology.

According to Rogers (1962), technology adoption can be viewed as a 5-step process. Research done on technology adoption shows that different people move through these 5 steps at different rates, some people combine all the steps in one, while others never get past the assessment stage. The 5 steps are:

Awareness: In this process, potential users learn enough about the technology and its benefits to decide whether they will use the new technology or not.

Assessment: Here, potential users evaluate the usefulness and usability of the technology, and the ease or difficulty of adoption.

Acceptance: In this stage a potential user weighs the advantages/disadvantages and decide whether to acquire and adopt or use the technology, or decide not to adopt the technology.

Learning: Users develop the skills and knowledge required to use the technology effectively and may search for further information about it.

Usage: Users demonstrate appropriate and effective use of the technology to its fullest potential.

Rogers (1962), defined the rate of adoption as the relative speed with which members of a social system adopt an innovation. In describing how an innovation reaches critical mass, he outlines several strategies in order to help a technology reach this stage. These strategies are:

- Have an innovation adopted by a highly respected individual within a social network.
- Have the technology creating an instinctive desire for a specific innovation.
- Have it inject an innovation into a group of individuals who would readily use a technology and
- Provide positive reactions and benefits for early adopters of an innovation.

However, the rate of adoption of technologies in the agricultural sector is very low due to the unwillingness of the farmers to take risk of using new technologies with the fear that it will lead to losses or reduction in output. Sometimes, high cost of procuring new technology may reduce rate of adoption. In view of these, it becomes imperative to intensify efforts on adoption of research results and technologies for sustainable development and farmer's profitability through adoption of superior technologies and research packages.

The National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM) has made tremendous efforts in the design and development of simple agricultural technologies aimed at improving the income and livelihood of small scale farmers. These technologies can be broadly classified into roots and tubers, grains and cereals, fruits and vegetables, oil seeds and fibers. Adoption of agricultural technologies remains a viable strategy for making farmers economically viable and increase farm productivity.

The transmission of research information to farmers is a vital factor in the rapid development of agriculture. It is desirable that results of research are disseminated as widely as possible and not just stockpiled. The process of bridging the gap between research and farmer should always be encouraged by well-meaning governments and their agencies. NCAM and other Agricultural Research Institutes have made a great investment in agricultural development, yet farmers remain unaware and skeptical in taking full advantage of these technologies in the farmer's agro-ecological environments for maximum exploitation and adoption by the farmers with their full participation.

The broad objective of this study is the adoption of simple processing technologies developed by NCAM. The specific objectives include the following:

- i. Promote the use of NCAM developed technologies;

- ii. Carry out demonstration of NCAM processing technologies for awareness in neighboring communities; and
- iii. Assess the level of adoption of NCAM developed technologies in the study area.

Literature Review

The literature on agricultural technology adoption is vast and somewhat difficult to summarize in a hurry. Traditionally, economic analysis of agricultural technology adoption has focused on imperfect information, risk, uncertainty, institutional constraints, human capital, input availability and infrastructure as potential explanations for adoption decisions (Feder *et al.*, 1985; Foster and Roserizweig 1996; and Kohli and Singh 1997).

Increasing agricultural productivity is central to reducing poverty in technology adoption. Agriculture plays a unique role in reducing poverty. Partly this reflects the sheer number of poor people engaged in it. Around 75% of those surviving on less than US\$1 a day – the internationally agreed definition of absolute poverty – live in rural areas (IFAD, 2001) and agriculture is an important livelihood source. It is estimated that 70% of Sub-Sahara Africa's labour force and 67% of south Asian works in agriculture (Maxwell, 2001).

In Nigeria and other countries of the world, several adoption studies have been conducted. Most of these studies are based on an initial desire to gather basic information about the use of modern crop varieties and inputs and also identify constraints to technology adoption. A large number of these studies concentrate on analysis of the determinants of agricultural adoption at the farm level.

Bandiera and Rasul (2002) looked at social networks and technology adoption in Northern Mozambique and found that the probability of adoption is higher in farmers who discussed agriculture amongst themselves.

The spread of new technologies and its adoption has been impressive globally, particularly improved modern varieties; for example, improved cassava varieties have spread rapidly in parts of West Africa (Nweke *et al.*, 2002) and research undertaken in Nigeria in the 1970s was fundamental to the development of cassava resistant to mosaic virus in Uganda nearly two decades later (Otim-Nape *et al.*, 2000).

The study conducted by Franzel *et al.* (2002) on agro forestry research has led to the widespread adoption of improved fallows in eastern Zambia making an important contribution to soil fertility and increased yields. According to Landers (2001), the adoption of reduced tillage practices in Brazil has increased productivity on more than 500,000 hectares of farm land.

A study by Giroh *et al.* (2007) examined the adoption of rubber quality innovations among small holder rubber farmers in two farm settlements of Delta State, Nigeria. Their findings revealed that the non-adoption level of rubber quality innovations was 66.06% while 33.94% of them adopted all the rubber quality innovations. Their findings also indicated that the adoption of rubber quality innovations has significant relationship with education, extension unit and the use of trained tappers.

Oladele and Fawole (2007) in their studies on farmers' perception of the relevance of technologies generated by research institutes in south - western Nigeria in the area of land evaluation, machinery and equipment discovered that machinery equipment fabrication was significantly related to their perception. It was observed that perception of farmer of the relevance of technologies is affected by awareness of the technologies and the inherent characteristics of the technologies itself affect their perception and their relevance.

Ogunsumi *et al.* (2010), in their studies on "adoption pattern of farmers in south west, Nigeria; the case of maize and cassava farmers" discovered that only 36.06% of the respondents abandoned the adopted technology afterwards while 64.94% sustained the use. The major reasons for partial adoption of set of technologies were unavailability of capital, affordability of inputs, high cost of production due to ever rising inflation rate, low research and extension outreach to farmers due to poor funding of research and extension.

Babatunde (2009), examined the impact of agricultural technology on poverty reduction in rural Nigeria. The findings of the study indicated that participation in agricultural technology does not automatically lead to the reduction in poverty head count levels and does not disproportionately improve the income of the poorest adopters in comparison with the non-adopters. The study further revealed that differences in poverty status between adopters and non-adopters of new agricultural technologies (a combination of tube wells and pumps) introduced in rural Nigerian in the late 1980's and early 1990s are modest. However, new agricultural technology would not expressly lead to poverty reduction in poor countries.

A study by Dontsop *et al.* (2011), on “Impact of improved rice technology on income and poverty among rice farming household in Nigeria; A Local Average Treatment Effect

(LATE) Approach” revealed a robust positive and signifying impact of New Rice for Africa (NERICA) variety adoption on farm household income and welfare measured by per capita expenditure and poverty reduction. Specifically, the empirical results suggest that adoption of NERICA varieties raises household per capital expenditure and income by an average of 4730.96 and 63771.94 Nigeria Naira per cropping season respectively, thereby reducing their probability of falling below the poverty line.

Jacob *et al.* (2001), in their studies on adoption of improved cowpea technologies in the savanna ecology of Nigeria, showed that farmers in Northern Nigeria where the study was conducted have adopted the use of improved cowpea technologies at different rates with the improved varieties having the highest rate of adoption. The adoption of cowpea technology has improved the proportion of cowpea revenue in farm income, area of land cropped to cowpea, total cowpea output and the role of cowpea in the food security of the farm families. However, lack of information on some of the technology and unavailability to farmers for purchase in the markets, tend to slow down the adoption rate.

Methodology

This study was carried out in Ifelodun Local Government Area (LGA) of Kwara State, Nigeria. Ifelodun is the largest Local Government Area in Kwara State with an estimated population of about 206,042 and an estimated total land area of about 3,435Km² (NPC, 2006 and KWSMI, 2002). The area is located between latitude 7^o45'N and 9^o30'N and longitude 2^o30'E and 6^o35'E.

It is characterized by dry and wet season. The annual rainfall ranges between 1000mm and 1500mm. Average temperatures varies between 30^oc and 35^oc while humidity range from 35% to 60%. The major source of livelihood and occupation of the people in the area is farming. Farming is traditional in nature with emphasis on the cultivation of crops such as cassava, yam, maize, sorghum and vegetables like Okro, Amaranthus, etc (KWSMI, 2002 and Mohammed, 2008). Cassava and Okro are predominantly grown in the area; this informed the choice of the Centre to develop processing prototype machines for these crops in the study area (i.e Cassava peeling tool and Okra slizer).

A 2-stage sampling technique was employed for the study. The first stage involved the purposive selection of four communities namely; Ganmo, Fufu, Idofian and Jimba-Oja. Based on their relative proximity to the Centre.

In the second stage, a random sampling technique was used to select 50 farmers from the selected communities based on their relative population size. Preliminary meetings were held with the village/community leaders to sensitize them on their relevance in mobilizing the farmers in their domain for the adoption of NCAM developed processing technologies.

The technologies to be adopted were demonstrated to the farmers while arrangement was made for publicity, press coverage (Radio jingles) during the demonstration after which the farmers were provided with the samples for their private use.

The data used for this study was basically primary data. This involved the use of an interview schedule with a structured questionnaire administered to the farmers. Relevant data collected include; socio-economic characteristics, sources of information on research results/technologies, adoption of technologies and constraints militating against adoption of NCAM processing technologies.

Descriptive statistics that was used include ratios, frequencies and percentages. This was used to analyze the constraints associated with the adoption of NCAM developed technologies.

Results and Discussions

The result from the study as presented in Table 1 showed a positive indicator that the adoption of these two NCAM technologies will enhance their livelihood. Table 2 showed that 70% were not aware of cassava peeling tools and 56% were not aware of okro slicer despite the relative proximity of NCAM to the selected communities. The level of awareness in the okro slicer (44.4%) is higher than that of peeling tool (30%). The lower level of awareness could be due to insufficiency of extension materials such as posters, bulletins, radio programs among others for the two newly introduced technologies before their adoption. Table 3 showed that 26.7% were aware that NCAM had tractors, 40% were aware of cassava lifter and 33.3% cassava press. This implies that generally, farmers were not aware of a lot of agricultural processing technologies developed by NCAM. It is therefore imperative that aggressive publicity should be carried out to create awareness about these NCAM technologies.

Table 4 shows that majority (62%) of the respondents had strong desire to adopt NCAM Cassava Peeling Tool. While 38% had less desire. This implies that majority of the farmers would want NCAM technology as a replacement to their old local technology. This finding is also similar for NCAM Okro slicer. Table 5 showed that 80% and 74% of the respondents agreed that the cassava peeling tool and okro slicer were respectively affordable compared to the local technology. In Table 6, 82% and 93% of the respondents confirmed that NCAM Cassava peeling tool and okro slicer respectively were compatible with their local technology which implies that the level of assimilation of these two NCAM technologies by the respondents is high. To further probe into the compatibility of the two technologies, the respondents were asked to objectively state how frequently they use the NCAM technologies in Table 7. 32% said they frequently use NCAM peeling tool while 41% used NCAM okro slicer frequently. This implies that the respondents will continue to use and adopt the two new technologies.

The respondents were asked the sources of information about the technologies to know whether the information on the two technologies were obtained only from the NCAM staff or from other sources. Table 8 reveals that majority of the respondents (80%) and (63%) knew about the two technologies from NCAM staff for cassava peeling tool and okro slicer respectively; 12% and 37% of the respondents respectively got their information through family and friends. This result agrees with that of Mohammed and Wanaso (1993) who reported that 58% of farmers in the western zone of Plateau State ADP got their information through friends and neighbors. Only 8% of the respondents got information on cassava peeler from extension agents, while for okro slicer there was none. It is clear that information from NCAM staff are more effective than other sources available. Perhaps channel of communication involved a one-to-one interaction. This findings support the report of Mohammed *et al.*, 2014 who stated that the use of information sources are significantly related to the adoption behavior of farmers. Extension agents are supposed to be the most effective and reliable source of information on technologies to the respondents. However, they are not readily available and accessible in NCAM. Availability and accessibility of extension services have been reported in many parts of sub-sahara Africa, Nigeria inclusive as a limiting factor for increased agricultural productivity (Eze *et al.*, 2006; Junge *et al.*, 2009). Farmers who are more exposed to formal extension information have a high propensity towards adoption than those with less exposure. In summary, imperfect information constitutes constraints to adoption.

For farmers to adopt an improved agricultural technology, they pass through many stages such as awareness, interest, trial evaluation and adoption (Mohammed *et al.*, 2014).

It is believed that the adoption of new agricultural technology, such as NCAM peeling tool and NCAM okro slicer could lead to significant increases in agricultural productivity and stimulate the transition from low productivity in subsistence agriculture to a high productivity agro-industrial economy (World Bank, 2008). The response on the level of adoption of NCAM peeling tool and okro slicer is presented in Table 9. The result indicated that 82% for peeling tool and 88.9% for okro slicer showed the keen interest and willingness to adopt the two technologies. The high level of interest developed by the respondents and the rate of adoption associated with the use of these technologies is as shown in figures 1, 2, 3 and 4 which implies that farmers in the area were aware of the fact that NCAM technologies will provide an attractive opportunity for them to make better economic gains. The follow-up visits by NCAM staff after the distribution of these two technologies for the farmers' private use may be the major reason for the high level of adoption of the technologies. In Table 10, 24% of the respondents stated that the peeling tool was very effective, 62% said it was effective while 14% said it was not effective. On the other hand, 52% confirmed that the okro slicer technology was very effective, while 48% respondents claimed it was effective and no respondents said it was not effective. Therefore, one can conclude that okro slicer could be a good replacement for the local knives. Also, Table 11 revealed that the two NCAM technologies extended to the respondents were adjudged as fast and convenient in use. 70% said NCAM cassava peeling tool was convenient while 78% said same for NCAM okroslicer. 30% and 22% respondents respectively stated that the two technologies were not convenient.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Agricultural development depends to a great extent, on the willingness and ability of the farmers to make use of the new technology as developed in NCAM. New technologies in agricultural development are of little value until they can be put to use for economic and social well-being of the people involved. The findings in this study have revealed that the respondents' interests, affordability as well as subsequent adoption indicated that adoption of NCAM cassava peeling tool and NCAM okro slicer improves farmer's livelihood, income and make their work faster and efficient.

It is therefore noteworthy to mention that the results from this study has exposed the strength of NCAM extension services and the need for a holistic approach on the issue of adoption of new technology so that NCAM agricultural processing technologies can be extended to farmers within and outside the state to increase farmers' income, reduce poverty and boost food security.

The contribution of a technology to economic growth can only be realized when and if the new technology is widely used. The result from the findings of the research work showed clearly the level of adoption of these two technologies as evident from the respondents' submission. Therefore, based on the motive of the development of these technologies to make agriculture more attractive and productive to the farmers, the following recommendations are proffered:

1. There is need for adequate publicity of NCAM technologies to create awareness among farmers and the general public.
2. NCAM staff with extension background should be fully involved from the planning stage for technologies to be extended in other to ensure the course of technology adoption.
3. Farmers should be encouraged to organize themselves into associations or groups such as cooperatives societies so that new ideas and technologies can easily be extended to them. This can enhance technology adoption and access to other services that may improve their welfare.
4. The extension component of the Centre should be strengthened to enable it meet the challenges of technology assimilation and adoption.

Table 1: Contribution of NCAM Technologies to the Respondent's Source of Livelihood

Technology	Variable	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent
Cassava peeling tool	Main	20	40.0	40.0
	Minor	30	60.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	
Okro slicer	Main	10	37.0	37.0
	Minor	17	63.0	100.0
	Total	27	100.0	

Source: Field Survey

Table 2 Awareness of NCAM Technologies by the Respondents

Technology	Variable	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent
Cassava peeling tool	Yes	15	30.0	30.0
	No	35	70.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	
Okro slicer	Yes	12	44.4	44.4
	No	15	55.6	100.0
	Total	27	100.0	

Source: Field Survey

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Table 3 Awareness of other NCAM Technologies

	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent
Hand tractor	4	26.7	26.7
Cassava lifter	6	40.0	66.7
Cassava processing	5	33.3	100.0
Total	15	100.0	

Source: Field Survey

Table 4: Aspiration of NCAM Technology

Technology	Variables	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent
Cassava peeling tool	Yes	31	62.0	62.0
	No	19	38.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	
Okro slicer	Yes	13	48.1	48.1
	No	14	51.9	100.0
	Total	27	100.0	

Source: Field Survey

Table 5: Affordability of NCAM Technologies

Adoption Study	Variables	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent
Cassava Peeling Tool	NCAM Peeling Tools	40	80.0	80.0
	NCAM Okro Slicer	2	4.0	84.0
	Both	8	16.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	
Okro Slicer	NCAM Peeling Tools	2	7.4	7.4
	NCAM Okro Slicer	20	74.1	81.5
	Both	5	18.5	100.0
	Total	27	100.0	

Source: Field Survey

Table 6: Compatibility of NCAM Technologies

Technology	Variables	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent
Cassava Peeling Tool	Yes	41	82.0	82.0
	No	9	18.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	
Okro Slicer	Yes	25	92.6	92.6
	No	2	7.4	100.0
	Total	27	100.0	

Source: Field Survey

Table 7: Frequency of Use of NCAM Technologies

Technology	Variables	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent
Cassava Peeling Tool	Local Knife	34	68.0	68.0
	NCAM Peeling Tools	16	32.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	
Okro Slicer	Local Knife	16	59.3	59.3
	NCAM Okro Slicer	11	40.7	100.0
	Total	27	100.0	

Source: Field Survey

Table 8: Sources of information about NCAM Technologies

Technology	Variables	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent
Cassava Peeling Tool	Family & Friend	6	12.0	12.0
	NCAM Staff	40	80.0	92.0
	Extension Agents	4	8.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	
Okro Slicer	Family & Friend	10	37.0	37.0
	NCAM Staff	17	63.0	100.0
	Extension Agents	0	0.0	
	Total	27	100.0	

Source: Field Survey

Table 9: Adoption Level of NCAM Technologies

Technology	Variables	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent
Cassava Peeling Tool	Yes	41	82.0	82.0
	No	9	18.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	
Okro Slicer	Yes	24	88.9	88.9
	No	3	11.1	100.0
	Total	27	100.0	

Source: Field Survey

Table 10: Effectiveness of NCAM Technologies

Technology	Variables	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent
Cassava Peeling Tool	Very Effective	12	24.0	24.0
	Effective	31	62.0	88.0
	Not Effective	7	14.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	
Okro Slicer	Very Effective	14	51.9	51.9
	Effective	13	48.1	100.0
	Not Effective	0	0.0	
	Total	27	100.0	

Source: Field Survey

Table 11: Convenience of NCAM Technologies

Technology	Variables	Frequency	Percent	Cum. Percent
Cassava Peeling Tool	Local Knife	25	30.0	30.0
	NCAM Peeling Tools	35	70.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	
Okro Slicer	Local Knife	6	22.2	22.2
	NCAM Okro Slicer	21	77.8	100.0
	Total	27	100.0	

Source: Field Survey

Fig. 1: NCAM Cassava Peeling tool in operation Fig. 2: Peeled Cassava tuber by the adopters

Fig. 3: NCAM Okro Slicer in use by an adopters Fig. 4: Sliced Okro with NCAM Okro Slicer

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